

Highlights

Return connectedness between energy commodities and stock markets: New evidence from 31 energy sector companies in Europe

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- We examine connectedness among oil, gas, and 31 European energy companies.
- We find connectedness between examined equity markets and oil, mostly in extrema.
- Gas is the most disconnected asset in the system.
- The largest companies from the oil & gas industry are the main shock contributors.
- Remaining companies are shock receivers and transmit some spillovers in extrema.

Return connectedness between energy commodities and stock markets: New evidence from 31 energy sector companies in Europe^{*,**}

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

return connectedness
Brent oil
gas
energy companies
COVID-19
Russia-Ukraine war

ABSTRACT

The prices of oil and gas significantly affect the world economy, and their fluctuations influence the financial and economic stability of many countries. This study considers the relationship among Brent crude oil, TTF natural gas price shocks, and the 31 European largest companies from the energy sector. We employ a connectedness framework of Diebold-Yilmaz to investigate the static and time-varying connectedness of commodity returns against the equity market. Our sample period ranges from March 2018 to December 2023, comprising the COVID-19 pandemic and the period of the Russo-Ukraine war. We investigate connectedness in the center and in the tails of the return distributions. We show that the overall connectedness reached its maximum at the beginning of the COVID-19 crisis. The role of oil changed from net receiver during the pandemic to a net transmitter in extrema afterward, while gas switched from shock absorber to being disconnected. The main contributors to the connectedness in the system in the median are the biggest companies from developed markets and the oil & gas sub-sector. Other companies generate fewer shocks to the markets. They mainly contribute to the connectedness in extrema.

1. Introduction

The prices of oil and gas significantly affect the world economy, and fluctuations in their values have a direct impact on fuel prices, food prices, inflation, and thus the financial stability of countries. This impact changes over time and depends on the current economic situation (Jawadi, Cheffou and Bu, 2023). According to the U.S. Energy Information Administration fossil fuels supply approximately 80% of the total energy. Analysis of the oil and gas market is important for investors, producers, consumers, and policymakers as they try to understand how sensitive these markets are to the changing economic environment and how much they themselves shape the environment. This paper considers the relationship between Brent crude oil and TTF natural gas price shocks and the 31 largest European companies from the energy sector.

Brent crude oil is considered one of the most important varieties of crude oil all over the world due to its high quality and stability. It is often used as a benchmark for oil prices in Europe. Dutch TTF Natural Gas is recognized as leading in Europe, having the highest and growing volume of trade (Papież, Rubaszek, Szafranek and Śmiech, 2022). Moreover, Szafranek and Rubaszek (2023) indicate that before the Russian invasion of Ukraine, TTF played a dominant role regarding price connectedness among major European gas markets. Most countries heavily depend on oil and gas imports; therefore, they closely monitor the changes in both markets and take appropriate actions to secure energy supplies and market stability.

The Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 forced a change in the direction of supplies of energy commodities. The Western countries' solidarity with Ukraine resulted in them being cut off from Russian raw materials and fuels. That, in turn, affected costs and ultimately translated into the price paid by consumers. Moreover, according to Adekoya, Asl, Oliyide and Izadi (2023), the war has a stronger direct influence on the persistence of oil and the European stock markets than the non-European stock markets. Thus, it seems to be of high priority nowadays to reveal

* This document is the result of the research project 2022/47/B/HS4/01194 "The impact of the Russo-Ukrainian conflict on prices and volatility of energy and crop commodities, and risk perception of European Union economies", funded by the National Science Center in Poland.

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the connectedness patterns between these two energy commodities and the stocks of those European companies, which are the most important for energy security.

Stock markets are affected by oil prices throughout two main channels (Asadi, Roubaud and Tiwari, 2022; B. and Paul, 2021). The first one corresponds to business operating costs. Rising oil prices can result in higher costs and directly reduce corporate earnings. The second channel is via a global market. An increase in oil prices can cause a reduction in the discount rate through inflationary pressure and lead to an adverse reaction in the stock market. Moreover, crude oil volatility increases in response to major political, financial, and natural events (Karali and Ramirez, 2014).

Natural gas has gradually become a significant factor affecting economic activity and plays a similar role to crude oil in the economic system (Geng, Chen, Ji and Liu, 2021). A growing number of empirical studies document a close relationship between energy and financial markets using various methods. Some studies apply GARCH-type models to investigate the linkages between markets from a volatility spillover perspective (Arouri, Jouini and Nguyen, 2012; Mollick and Assefa, 2013; Wang and Liu, 2015; Kumar, Singh and Kumar, 2021). Copulas are widely used to identify the dependence structure between markets. They allow one to focus on the tails of the distributions and model the nonlinear tail dependence structure (Mensi, Hammoudeh, Shahzad and Shahbaz, 2017; Lin, Zhou, Jiang and Ou, 2021; Jiang and Ye, 2022; Boubaker and Larbi, 2022). Quantile dependence methods are powerful econometric tools for considering the economic impacts of events exceeding the mean. They are used to verify the asymmetry in spillovers between extremal positive and negative movements in energy and stock markets (Hamdi, Aloui, Alqahtani and Tiwari, 2019; Wen, Wang, Ma and Wang, 2019; Naeem, Hasan, Arif, Balli and Shahzad, 2020; Adekoya and Oliyide, 2021). Granger causality is a concept of causality that reveals a lead-lag relationship between markets, reflecting their predictability and temporal precedence (Acaravci, Ozturk and Kandir, 2012; Ding, Kim and Park, 2016; Liu, Ding, Li, Jiang, Wu and Lv, 2017; Das, Kumar, Tiwari, Shahbaz and Hasim, 2018). The main drawback of all these approaches is that they are inconvenient for modeling a large set of instruments or markets. In contrast, the Diebold and Yilmaz (2012) model is able to accommodate a large number of time series simultaneously. Moreover, it allows one to compare directional market shock spillovers between assets in the considered system.

In this paper, we conduct a deeper analysis of oil and gas markets and discuss their connectedness with Europe's largest companies operating in the energy sector. The research period is from March 16, 2018, to December 29, 2023; therefore, it covers the pre-COVID-19, COVID-19 pandemic, and the Russia-Ukraine war. Our study differs from the currently published papers in the following aspects. First, most of the articles concentrate on US or Asian stock markets, and only a minority of them relate to European markets. Secondly, they analyze stock market indices, treating them as benchmarks of financial sectors. However, indices – by definition – track the price performance of an underlying group of company shares and, therefore, cannot reflect complexity and dependencies between individual assets. To overcome these hurdles, we focus on the connectedness of stocks of the largest 31 companies from the energy sector quoted in European stock exchanges. We focus on energy companies from developed and emerging markets, which at the end of 2023 were the constituents of two indices, STOXX Europe 600 Energy and STOXX Eastern Europe 300 Energy. Thus, we study firms from oil and gas exporting as well as importing countries. Eventually, we consider energy firms with relatively similar business profiles (see Table 1).

The major contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows. First, we analyze connectedness in returns among crude oil, natural gas, and 31 stocks of energy companies quoted in European exchanges using the framework of Diebold and Yilmaz (2012). The study concerns firms whose business profile is related to the energy market. These companies directly affect the operating costs of all other firms and households who are energy consumers. Thus, they are responsible for energy security in their countries and the entire region. Second, although all considered firms operate in the energy market, they are not homogeneous and function in different business environments. We aim to explain which factor (firm size, country of origin, business profile) plays a dominant role in the transmission of price shocks in Europe and how the role changes in the face of different geopolitical risks affecting the world economy. We study the dynamics in the spillover applying the Time-Varying Parameter VAR (TVP-VAR) approach (Antonakakis, Chatziantoniou and Gabauer, 2020). We demonstrate that the largest oil & gas companies from developed markets (TotalEnergies, Eni, Shell, Aker, BP, Equinor, Repsol, Galp Energia SGPS, OMV, Subsea 7, and Tenaris) as net transmitters of shocks, whereas the remaining companies are the net recipients. The maximum level of spillovers among the considered assets appeared at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic. Third, this empirical study determines the extent of directional return spillover from oil and natural gas commodities to energy firms. Thus, we measure the vulnerability of these companies to energy price shocks. We find that the oil market was a substantial contributor of return shocks to the examined stocks, whereas we report no significant transmission between gas and stock markets. Fourth, for a deeper

analysis, our study distinguishes between negative and positive return spillovers among markets, which allows us to account for asymmetry. To investigate connectedness in quantiles, we apply the novel quantile frequency method based on QVAR estimates (Chatziantoniou, Gabauer and Stenfors, 2021). We show that the largest stocks from developed markets transmit shocks in the median area, whereas Brent oil and stocks from emerging markets – in low and high quantiles.

The remainder of this study is structured as follows. Section 2 briefly reviews the literature. Section 3 describes the methods used in the empirical part. Section 4 provides the data and the descriptive statistics. Section 5 discusses the empirical findings, and Section 6 delivers concluding remarks.

2. Literature review

This section briefly summarizes the empirical results of recent studies on connectedness between stock markets and energy commodities (or their proxies) in the spirit of Diebold and Yilmaz (2012).

Spillover effects between stock markets and oil depend strongly on whether the markets represent the supply or demand side. It results from the fact that oil-exporting countries tend to be more responsive to the oil price due to their direct dependence on it as a source of income. Umar, Trabelsi and Zaremba (2021) analyze the relationship between the major world's oil-producing countries and emerging markets – the major world's oil importers – decomposing the oil shocks into daily components related to demand, supply, and risk shocks. The empirical study applies the country-specific MSCI total return equity indices over the period from January 2005 to July 2020. The authors find a moderate connectedness between examined equity markets and oil shocks, in terms of return and volatility, with an unprecedented level during the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, the volatility of oil-exporting countries contributes more to the volatility connectedness. Kliber and Łęt (2022) document that shocks from Brent seem to influence stock markets from countries being the net oil exporters (OSEAX and RTS) the most, as compared to the impact of oil prices on the other 20 indices representing importers. More shocks are transmitted from those markets to Brent than the other way around. In a similar vein, Chang, Chang and Lee (2023), examining return and volatility contagion among the oil and the stock markets of BRICS, indicate that stock markets from major BRICS exporters (Brazil and Russia) are net transmitters of shocks, and the stock markets in China and India are net receivers. On the other hand, Escribano, Koczar, Jareño and Esparcia (2023) report less intuitive results: stock markets within oil-exporting countries, such as Norway or Russia, are classified as net receivers of shocks, whereas the indices representative for developed markets, such as S&P 500 and DAX, are net transmitters of shocks to emerging markets in terms of volatility. That is because the developed markets play a dominant role in the mechanism of global spillover. Zhang, Wang and Li (2023) show that spillover transmission in geopolitical risks differs between the developed and developing regions. North American and South and West European markets are the main spillover-givers of geopolitical risk, while the other regions switch between the transmitters and recipients over time.

Connectedness between markets is time-varying, and it changes rapidly in response to different geopolitical or financial events, as well as natural disasters. Most of the recent research has concentrated on two specific periods for energy markets, encompassing the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russia-Ukraine war. Guru, Pradhan and Bandaru (2023) report substantial bidirectional spillovers between the oil market and G7 plus Indian and Chinese stock markets. Numerous studies document increased risk contagion effects in various stock markets and sectors during the outbreak of COVID-19 (Asadi, Pham, Nguyen, Do and Brooks, 2023; Chang et al., 2023; Dai and Zhu, 2022; Luo, Qu, Su and Dong, 2024). Moreover, Mensi, Al Rababa'a, Vo and Kang (2021) find asymmetry between bad and good news in Chinese sector stock markets. The degree of negative return spillovers is higher than those of positive spillovers, indicating evidence of leverage effects. The same conclusions were formulated by Si Mohammed, Tedeschi, Mallek, Tarczyńska-Łuniewska and Zhang (2023), who revealed asymmetric connectedness between Brent and stock markets, with negative information having a stronger influence than the positive one. The results emphasize the need to design more efficient trading strategies adapted to the market condition. Scholars document that the spillover effect between the oil market and stock markets during the Ukraine-Russia war was much lower compared to the pandemic, mainly due to the exposure of the military conflict at the regional (European) level – not to the global one (Naeem, Gul, Shafiullah, Karim and Lucey, 2024). Si Mohammed et al. (2023) report that the S&P 500 was less affected and partially independent of the shocks related to the Russian-Ukrainian conflict compared to European and Asian markets. European stock markets demonstrate higher peaks in the semi-variance connection with Brent, reflecting the sensitivity of DAX and CAC 40 to energy prices during the war. On the other hand, Adekoya, Oliyide, Yaya and Al-Faryan (2022) reported the strengthened spillover effect of oil on the S&P 500 index during the war. Moreover, oil changed

from being a net receiver of spillovers before the war to a net transmitter after it. Nonetheless, European firms are more related to shocks from energy commodities and this particular geopolitical turmoil. Kumari, Kumar and Pandey (2023), employing the event study method, find that the markets geographically closer to the war zone and those with less efficient markets are significantly more affected by the conflict. On the other hand, Xing, Xu, Chen, Ouyang, Deng and Pan (2023) find the shift in the volatility transmission between stocks from traditional energy and renewable energy sub-sectors in China during the Russia–Ukraine war. According to the study, before the conflict, the traditional energy stocks acted mainly as spillover transmitters. However, after February 22, 2022, some of the renewable energy firms turned out to be the main risk transmitters, tending to influence other stocks in the system.

The natural gas market differs substantially from the crude oil market, in which prices are determined by global factors (Szafranek and Rubaszek, 2023). Instead, the natural gas market is geographically segmented into several local markets, with the leading source regions in Russia, the USA, and Western Asia (Kan, Chen, Wu, Chen and Chen, 2019). That makes the natural gas market disconnected from other markets compared to the oil market. Gong, Liu and Wang (2021) report strong asymmetry in the oil-gas relationship. The crude oil and heating oil futures market were the main net transmitters of volatility risk over 2015–2019, while the gasoline and natural gas futures markets were the net receivers. Moreover, the pairwise volatility spillover from the crude oil market had the most significant influence on the natural gas market.

Similar patterns of connectedness arise when the relationships between oil, gas, and stock markets are studied. For instance, Karkowska and Urjasz (2023) find that gas markets (TTF, Henry Hub and Japan/Korea Marker) were much less connected with the main stock market benchmarks for the US, Europe, and Asia, represented by the S&P 500, STOXX 600, and Hang Seng, as compared to the oil markets (WTI, Brent and Dubai). Moreover, the role of oil markets in the system varied from net transmitter to net recipient over the period August 1, 2014, to May 27, 2022, whereas gas markets were constantly the net recipients. The result supports the findings of Cao, Yang and Yu (2023) obtained using the Baruník and Křehlík (2018) model. During the financial crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic, financial market uncertainty (VIX), energy market uncertainty (OVX), and stock market volatility exerted a substantial influence on the natural gas market in the high-frequency band within 12 trading weeks – according to the study.

To sum up, existing literature includes results on the relationship between oil price shocks and equity markets in various aspects. Most of them relate to the dependence between energy commodities and stock indices – thus, the linkage between the variables is mainly throughout the global market channel. We extend the literature by providing new insights into the European energy market, investigating the connectedness of energy commodities and stocks of firms from the energy sector. The empirical study employs a connectedness approach in the static and dynamic framework, considering spillovers in median and extreme returns.

3. Methodology

3.1. Diebold and Yilmaz method

To assess the connectedness between the variables under study, we adopt the approach of Diebold and Yilmaz (2012). To calculate it, one first estimates a vector autoregressive (VAR) model and next, decomposes the variance-covariance matrix of the forecast error.

Let $\mathbf{x}_t = (x_{1,t}; \dots; x_{N,t})$, where $t = 1, \dots, T$ denote a covariance stationary N -variate process represented by the VAR model of order p :

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \Phi_1 \mathbf{x}_{t-1} + \Phi_2 \mathbf{x}_{t-2} + \dots + \Phi_p \mathbf{x}_{t-p} + \epsilon_t. \quad (1)$$

The matrices Φ_i are coefficient matrices, ϵ_t is a white noise with covariance matrix Σ , which most often is not a diagonal one. The model can be rewritten as (Greene, 2003):

$$\Phi(L)\mathbf{x}_t = \epsilon_t, \quad (2)$$

where $\Phi(L) = [I_N - \Phi_1 L - \dots - \Phi_p L^p]$, and I_N denotes the identity matrix. The VAR process has the vector moving average, VMA(∞), representation if the roots of $|\Phi(z)|$ lie outside the unit circle (Greene, 2003):

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \Psi(L)\epsilon_t. \quad (3)$$

Since $\Psi(L)$ contains infinite lags, it needs to be approximated with the moving average coefficients Ψ_h at $h = 1, \dots, H$ horizons. As already mentioned, the connectedness measures are calculated based on the decomposition of the variance-covariance matrix of the forecast error, where the forecast is set for horizons $h = 1, \dots, H$. That enables one to assess the contribution of shocks of a given variable to the whole system (Baruník and Křehlík, 2018).

The first version of the connectedness index was based on the Cholesky decomposition, and the drawback of this approach was that the results changed together with the ordering of variables (Diebold and Yilmaz, 2009). To overcome it, in the further version, Diebold and Yilmaz (2012) applied a generalized variance decomposition of Pesaran and Shin (1998):

$$(\theta_H)_{j,k} = \frac{\sigma_{kk}^{-1} \sum_{h=0}^{H-1} \left((\Psi_h \Sigma)_{j,k} \right)^2}{\sum_{h=0}^{H-1} (\Psi_h \Sigma \Psi_h')_{j,j}}, \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma_{kk} = (\Sigma)_{kk}^{-1}$ and Ψ_h is a $(N \times N)$ matrix of moving average coefficients at lag h .

The $(\theta_H)_{j,k}$ denotes the contribution of the k -th variable to the variance of the forecast error of the element j , at horizon H . Each entry is normalized by the row sum (Diebold and Yilmaz, 2012):

$$(\tilde{\theta}_H)_{j,k} = \frac{(\theta_H)_{j,k}}{\sum_{k=1}^N (\theta_H)_{j,k}}. \quad (5)$$

As a consequence, the rows of the variance decomposition matrix sum to 1:

$$\sum_{k=1}^N (\tilde{\theta}_H)_{j,k} = 1,$$

and:

$$\sum_{j,k=1}^N (\tilde{\theta}_H)_{j,k} = N.$$

The authors distinguish between the total and directional connectedness. The total connectedness measure (TCI) is the share of variance of the forecast errors other than own ones – i.e. the ratio of the sum of the off-diagonal elements to the sum of the entire matrix (Diebold and Yilmaz, 2012):

$$C_H = \frac{\sum_{j \neq k} (\tilde{\theta}_H)_{j,k}}{\sum \tilde{\theta}_H} = 1 - \frac{\text{Tr} \{ \tilde{\theta}_H \}}{\sum \tilde{\theta}_H}. \quad (6)$$

The symbol $\text{Tr} \{ \cdot \}$ denotes the trace of the matrix from the other variables in the system.

Directional connectedness measures the contribution of all other markets (variables) ($j \neq k$) to the variance of the forecast error of the given market (variable) j (connectedness FROM others) (Diebold and Yilmaz, 2014):

$$C_H^j = \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq j}}^N (\tilde{\theta}_H)_{j,k}. \quad (7)$$

Similarly, one calculates the contribution of the j -th market to the forecast error variance of all other markets $k \neq j$ (connectedness TO others) (Diebold and Yilmaz, 2014):

¹In the equation above $(\mathbf{A})_{ij}$ denotes the i -th row and j -th column of matrix \mathbf{A} .

$$C_H^j = \sum_{\substack{k=1 \\ k \neq j}}^N (\tilde{\theta}_H)_{k,j}. \quad (8)$$

The net connectedness is defined as the difference between the spillovers sent to other markets and received from them (Diebold and Yilmaz, 2012; Diebold and Yilmaz, 2014):

$$C_H^j = C_H^j - C_H^{j\cdot}. \quad (9)$$

Eventually, one can calculate net pairwise directional connectedness (NPDC) as:

$$C_H^{j,k} = (\tilde{\theta}_H)_{k,j} - (\tilde{\theta}_H)_{j,k}. \quad (10)$$

The NPDC between markets j and k is interpreted as the difference between the gross spillovers transmitted from market j to market k and those transmitted from k to j .

3.2. Quantile connectedness

Quantile connectedness measures are based on QVAR estimates (Chatziantoniou et al., 2021):

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \boldsymbol{\mu}(\tau) + \sum_{i=1}^p \boldsymbol{\Phi}_i(\tau) \mathbf{x}_{t-i} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_t(\tau), \quad (11)$$

where $\tau \in (0; 1)$ represents a quantile, $\boldsymbol{\mu}(\tau)$ is a $k \times 1$ -dimensional conditional mean vector, $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_i(\tau)$ is $k \times k$ -dimensional coefficient matrix, while $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is an error vector which has a $k \times k$ -dimensional variance-covariance matrix, $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}(\tau)$.

Again, to calculate connectedness measures, one needs to transform the QVAR to QVMA representation (Chatziantoniou et al., 2021):

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \boldsymbol{\mu}(\tau) + \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \boldsymbol{\Psi}_i(\tau) \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_{t-i}. \quad (12)$$

Connectedness measures are calculated analogously to the base case.

4. Data

Our sample consists of weekly data from 14 European capital markets operating in the energy sector over six years, from March 16, 2018, to December 29, 2023. As a proxy for the European crude oil and gas markets, we employ the weekly price series of ICE Europe Brent Crude (LOCc1) and Natural Gas TTF Netherlands (TRNLTTFFVYc1), respectively. Data on crude oil, gas, and stock prices (expressed in USD) comes from the Refinitiv Eikon database. Our choice of energy companies is based on the constituents of two indices, STOXX Europe 600 Energy and STOXX Eastern Europe 300 Energy, at the end of 2023. These constituents mirror the FTSE Russell classification of developed and emerging markets. If the company prices were not available in the Refinitiv Eikon database during the entire period under review, the company was not included in the study (six companies). Table 1 presents a short description of 31 energy stocks listed in the developed and emerging markets included in the study.

The largest energy companies in Europe have their headquarters in Great Britain, France, Norway, and Italy. Other players among the top ten are located in Denmark, Finland, Spain, and Poland (Table 1). Shell PLC is the first on the list of the largest energy companies in Europe by market capitalization (USD 211.11 billion at the end of 2023). It is an international energy company headquartered in London, specialized in the exploration, production, refining, and marketing of oil and natural gas. Shell also invests in renewable energy, focusing on wind and solar power. As of December 2023, the second largest company, TotalEnergies SE, had a capitalization of USD 159.87 billion. It is a

France-based oil and gas company. This multi-energy company produces and markets fuels, natural gas, and electricity in France, Europe, North America, Africa, and internationally. The company also invests in renewable energy, with a focus on solar and wind power. The next company is BP PLC headquartered in London, with market capitalization two times lower than Shell PLC. It is a multinational energy company, dealing with operations in the oil and gas, renewable energy, and petrochemical sectors. The next two companies are Equinor ASA and Eni SpA, with a market capitalization of USD 99.08 billion and USD 56.09 billion, respectively (at the end of 2023). The first company is a Norway-based international energy firm that engages in the exploration, production, refining, transportation, and marketing of petroleum, wind and solar energy in Norway and internationally. Equinor is responsible for 70% of oil and gas production in Norway, being the largest producer of these raw materials in Europe (except Russia). The second company is Italy-based and engages in the exploration, extracting, development, manufacturing, and marketing of crude oil and natural gas, oil-based fuels, gas-fired power, and energy products from renewable sources. Orlen SA is the only company included in both considered indices. It is a Poland-based company active in the oil and gas sectors. As of December 2023, the market capitalization of Orlen was USD 19.34 billion, while at the end of 2021, it was only USD 1.70 billion, since the company completed the acquisition of Grupa Lotos in August 2022 and PGNiG in December 2022.

Table 2 (Appendix) shows the descriptive statistics of the weekly returns for energy stocks, oil, and gas. First, in all cases, we observe positive and significant correlations between energy stock markets and oil. The market of Norway shows the highest correlations. Second, in most cases, the correlations between the energy stock markets and gas present insignificant correlations. Third, the correlations between developed stock markets, on the one hand, and energy commodities, on the other hand, are higher than those between emerging stock markets and energy commodities.

Table 1
The list of stocks used in the study.

Stock	Stock ticker	Stock exchange	Industry	Market cap (billion USD)
Shell PLC	SHEL.L	London SE	Oil & Gas Operations	211.11
BP PLC	BP.L	London SE	Oil & Gas Operations	100.61
Harbour Energy PLC	HBR.L	London SE	Oil & Gas Operations	3.03
Enean PLC	ENOG.L	London SE	Oil & Gas Operations	2.44
TotalEnergies SE	TTEF.PA	Euronext Paris	Oil & Gas Operations	159.87
Gaztransport et Technigaz SA	GTT.PA	Euronext Paris	Oil Well Services & Equipment	4.89
Eni SpA	ENI.MI	Milan SE	Natural Gas Utilities	56.09
Snam SpA	SRG.MI	Milan SE	Natural Gas Utilities	17.22
Tenaris SA	TENR.MI	Milan SE	Construction - Supplies & Fixtures	20.51
Equinor ASA	EQNR.OL	Oslo SE	Oil & Gas Operations	99.08
Aker BP ASA	AKRBP.OL	Oslo SE	Oil & Gas Operations	18.41
Subsea 7 SA	SUBC.OL	Oslo SE	Oil Well Services & Equipment	4.39
Nel ASA	NEL.OL	Oslo SE	Chemical Manufacturing	1.14
Vestas Wind Systems A/S	VWS.CO	Copenhagen SE	Misc. Capital Goods	31.93
Repsol SA	REP.MC	Madrid SE	Oil & Gas Operations	18.06
Enagas SA	ENAG.MC	Madrid SE	Natural Gas Utilities	4.40
Neste Oyj	NESTE.HE	Helsinki SE	Oil & Gas Operations	27.31
Galp Energia SGPS SA	GALP.LS	Euronext Lisbon	Oil & Gas Operations	12.00
OMV AG	OMVV.VI	Vienna SE	Oil & Gas Operations	14.36
Orlen SA	PKN.WA	Warsaw SE	Oil & Gas Operations	19.34
Jastrzebska Spolka Weglowa SA	JSW.WA	Warsaw SE	Coal	1.25
Lubelski Wegiel Bogdanka SA	LWBP.WA	Warsaw SE	Coal	0.29
Koc Holding AS	KCHOL.IS	Istanbul SE	Oil Well Services & Equipment	12.20
Turkiye Petrol Rafinerileri AS	TUPRS.IS	Istanbul SE	Oil & Gas Operations	9.35
Ippek Dogal Enerji Kaynaklari Arastirma ve Uretim AS	IPEKE.IS	Istanbul SE	Oil & Gas Operations	0.28
MOL Magyar Olajes Gazipari Nyrt	MOLB.BU	Budapest SE	Oil & Gas Operations	5.16
OMV Petrom SA	ROSNP.BX	Bucharest SE	Oil & Gas Operations	7.95
Societatea Nationala de Gaze Naturale Romgaz SA	SNG.BX	Bucharest SE	Oil & Gas Operations	4.29
Societatea Nationala de Transport Gaze Naturale Transgaz SA	TGN.BX	Bucharest SE	Oil Well Services & Equipment	0.79
Motor Oil Hellas Corinth Refineries SA	MORr.AT	Athens SE	Oil & Gas Operations	2.85
HELLENIQ ENERGY Holdings SA	HEPr.AT	Athens SE	Oil & Gas Operations	2.46

Note: Market cap means market capitalization at the end of 2023 (December 29, 2023). The horizontal line separates developed and emerging markets.

5. Empirical results

To investigate the connectedness between energy commodity and stock markets in Europe, we employ both a static and dynamic connectedness analysis. The static approach provides an overview of connectedness on average, whereas the dynamic approach shows the evolution of connectedness over time, given the impact of specific events. Finally, we use the quantile connectedness approach to deepen the connectedness analysis among assets under different market conditions and check the robustness of the results.

5.1. Static connectedness analysis

This section documents the static return connectedness across studied markets during the entire period and three sub-periods: pre-COVID-19, COVID-19, and the war in Ukraine. The first one covers the period from March 16, 2018, to the end of 2019. The beginning corresponds to the availability of Energean PLC quotations. The second period, from the beginning of 2020 to the end of 2021, covers the COVID-19 crisis, whereas the period from the beginning of 2022 to the end of 2023 – the war in Ukraine. We estimate the connectedness between returns based on the framework of Diebold and Yilmaz (2012). Since we analyze 33 assets, we use the LASSO-VAR(1) model and then examine generalized variance decompositions in a 4-week horizon.

We concentrate on the following connectedness measures: total directional TO (Eq. 8, Figure 1), FROM (Eq. 7, Figure 2), NET (Eq. 9, Figure 3), and net pairwise directional (Eq. 10, Figure 4). The variance decomposition matrix is available in the Online Appendix – Table A1 shows the results for the entire period, while Tables A2–A4 are for sub-periods.

System-wide (total) asset return connectedness (TCI, Eq. 6) amounts to 82% (Table A1). That is, on average over 80% of each asset's future return uncertainty is due to "non-own" shocks. Moreover, TCI is significantly higher during the COVID-19 (89%) and Ukraine war (76%) periods than in the pre-pandemic period (67%) (Tables A2–A4). This result corroborates previous studies, showing that return connectedness among oil and stock markets increases during COVID-19 (Balli, O Balli and Nguyen, 2023; Chang et al., 2023; Sevillano, Jareño, López and Esparcia, 2024; Zhang and Hamori, 2021). High TCI values indicate a close relationship among energy sector companies, especially during market turmoils. Eleven companies from developed markets send the highest percentage of uncertainty to other examined markets in Europe: TotalEnergies, Eni, Shell, Aker, BP, Equinor, Repsol, Galp Energia SGPS, OMV, Subsea 7, and Tenaris (Figure 1). It is interesting to note that a few companies from emerging markets (Orlen, MOL Magyar Olajes Gazipari Nyrt, HELLENiQ ENERGY Holdings, Motor Oil Hellas Corinth Refineries, OMV Petrom, and Romgaz) sent a rather large amount of future uncertainty to others during the COVID-19 period (Figure 1, turquoise bar). Moreover, this is the only period in which oil and all stock markets absorb similar proportions of shocks (Figure 2). In general, in the connectedness TO the system, we observe more considerable differences between assets than in the connectedness FROM the system.

In Figure 3, we plot the difference between connectedness TO and FROM, i.e. the net total directional connectedness of the system analyzed in this paper. A positive net total directional connectedness index indicates that the corresponding asset transmits more shocks to the whole asset system than it receives, acting as a net transmitter of return shocks. In contrast, a negative net total directional connectedness index indicates that the asset is a net receiver of shocks. We also use the network diagram to identify the recipients and contributors of overall spillovers more clearly (Figure 4). The net total directional connectedness indices of the eleven companies from the above-mentioned developed markets are positive in all subperiods, implying that these companies play the role of net transmitters of shocks in energy commodities and stock markets in Europe. Oil has shifted from a net transmitter to a net receiver of shocks in the system after the outbreak of COVID-19. In turn, companies from emerging markets usually receive more shocks than they transmit during all subperiods. However, the largest net recipients of shocks from the system are gas and two companies from developed markets: Nel and Vestas Wind Systems. These companies are not included in the oil & gas operations industry. The first is a Norway-based hydrogen company that delivers solutions to produce, store and distribute hydrogen from renewable energy. The second is a Denmark-based firm active within the wind power industry. Our results support the findings of Dai, Tang and Zhang (2023) that developed stock markets tend to have high connectivity and act as risk emitters in spillover networks (the oil and G20 stock markets), while developing stock markets tend to be risk receivers.

Concerning net pairwise directional connectedness (Figure 4), we can notice the highest asymmetry in the transmission of shocks between pairs of asset markets in the pre-pandemic period. Among all the connections, the transmission between Equinor and natural gas stands out throughout the entire period. The high value of the NPDC

index results from the increased transmission of the company's price shocks to the gas market during the pandemic and notably the war. Equinor is the largest gas producer on the Norwegian Continental Shelf. Furthermore, Norway boosted gas production by 8% in 2022 to satisfy the demand in Europe and became Europe's biggest supplier of natural gas to the region. This naturally tightened the link between these assets. To focus on the connectedness between individual energy stock markets and oil and gas markets, we show pairwise directional connectedness measures: oil TO others (Figure 5), oil FROM others (Figure 6), gas TO others (Figure 7), and gas FROM others (Figure 8). Oil return shocks were transmitted to the stock markets sub-group, mainly before the pandemic and during the war in Ukraine. As indicated in Figure 5, the developed stock markets of Norway, the UK, Finland, Portugal, and Italy, and the emerging stock market of Bulgaria appear to be the leading shock recipients from the oil market in the pre-COVID-19 period. During the war in Ukraine, the coal sub-sector companies from Poland joined this group. On the other hand, developed energy stock markets in Norway, the UK, Portugal, Italy, France, and Spain stand out as the dominant shock transmitters to the oil market in all sub-periods (Figure 6). Moreover, during the pandemic, several developing stock markets increase the transmission of shocks to the oil market, but transmit fewer shocks than most developed stock markets. Thus, we observe an interesting phenomenon: relatively low connectedness between oil and emerging energy stock markets in Europe, and higher connectedness between oil and developed energy stock markets, which declines in times of turmoil. According to Figure 7, the values of directional connectedness measure from gas to other markets are exceedingly low (generally do not exceed 2%). In addition, the values of directional connectedness from another market to the gas market are low (oscillate between 1% and 5%) (Figure 8). Only the transmission of return shocks to the gas market by Equinor is higher and similar to that of the oil market (7–9%). Therefore, we may conclude that the oil market is a significant contributor of return shocks to examined stocks from developed markets, but we find no significant transmission between gas and stocks. Furthermore, the relationship between oil shocks and developed stock markets is asymmetric, because the oil market appears to be more sensitive to stock return shocks. Our results support the findings of Dai and Zhu (2022) that WTI and gas are the net receivers of systematic shocks from stock markets. Karkowska and Urjasz (2023) explain the phenomenon in the following way. The stock market acts as a barometer for the entire economy. Therefore, all market shocks cause a sharp increase in the volatility of the returns of the stock index and later are transferred to other groups of assets, such as the oil and gas markets. Kilian and Park (2009); Conrad, Loch and Rittler (2014); Zhang and Wang (2019) explain that the oil market is a component of the global financial system and its price shocks should not be considered as exogenous in the oil-stocks relationship. Moreover, researchers document that speculative factors (related to buying crude not for current consumption but for future use) may play some role in shaping oil prices or that they co-move with them (see e.g. Dvir and Rogoff (2014), Vansteenkiste (2011), Fattouh, Kilian and Mahadeva (2013)). That explains why oil futures prices are also affected by shocks in global financial markets.

5.2. Dynamic connectedness analysis

To explore the time-varying return connectedness between assets, we use the TVP-VAR(1) model (Antonakakis et al., 2020) combined with the Diebold and Yilmaz connectedness approach. The latter is useful for our analysis as our data series are relatively short. We verify the robustness of our results by applying the LASSO method to estimate the parameters of the VAR(1) model, which can improve the accuracy and computational efficiency of the model (Dai et al., 2023). On the other hand, this method is sensitive to the size of the rolling window. This study uses the rolling LASSO-VAR(1) model with a fixed window size of 104 and 156 weeks and a 4-week forecast horizon.

We display the dynamic total connectedness index in Figure 9. This figure shows one substantial and many smaller spikes and drops in the total connectedness index, confirming the time-varying nature of the return connectedness. The highest overall connectedness was observed at the beginning of the COVID-19 crisis when the prices of oil, gas and stocks dropped, and TCI increased from almost 80% to 95% in early 2020. We also note the spike in total connectedness in late February 2022 and in the months following the Russian invasion of Ukraine, during which adverse geopolitical events on markets occurred, increasing economic uncertainty. However, TCI was notably lower than in the COVID-19 period (oscillated around 80%). Gong and Xu (2022) concluded that geopolitical act risk (i.e. widely understood uncertainty) drives connectedness changes across commodity markets more than geopolitical threats (associated mainly with military acts). Particularly, both the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 and the Hamas attack on Israel in October 2023 significantly increased the geopolitical risk, tripling and doubling the Geopolitical Risk Index, respectively. However, these events only resulted in a short-term increase in TCI by 2 and 3 percentage points, respectively.

Figure 1: Directional connectedness for oil, gas, and energy stocks: directional connectedness TO all others.

Figure 2: Directional connectedness for oil, gas, and energy stocks: directional connectedness FROM all others.

Next, we show the dynamic connectedness TO all other assets (Figure 10) and FROM all other assets (Figure 11). The results indicate higher change over time in the connectedness TO the system than in the connectedness FROM the system. TotalEnergies, Eni, Shell, BP, and Equinor are responsible for high values of transmitting shocks to other assets during the whole period. During the war in Ukraine, Equinor transmitted the most shocks whereas in the remaining periods, TotalEnergies and Eni played the role of main shock transmitters. The significant role of TotalEnergies and Eni may result from the importance of French and Italian economies in the European Union (EU). These countries

Figure 3: Directional connectedness for oil, gas, and energy stocks: NET total directional connectedness.

have the second and third largest economies in the EU, after Germany. Intra-EU trade accounts for 54% of France’s exports and 51% of Italy’s exports. On the other hand, in terms of imports, 66% and 58% come from EU Member States, respectively. These results are consistent with those obtained using the LASSO-VAR model in three sub-periods and the rolling LASSO-VAR approach. Thus, our findings emphasize the critical role of the large developed stock markets of the oil & gas industry in transmitting market shocks. Furthermore, the five largest energy stock markets (TotalEnergies, Eni, Shell, BP, and Equinor) and Repsol are persistent net risk (price changes) transmitters while emerging energy stock markets are consistently risk takers (Figure 12). The conclusion supports our earlier findings from the static approach. The role of oil, gas, and several companies from various sub-sectors is inconclusive due to distinct time-varying characteristics. Therefore, sections on quantile connectedness have been added to deepen the analysis of connectedness between assets under different market conditions.

5.3. Quantile connectedness – static and dynamic analysis

Using the static QVAR(1) connectedness approach (Chatziantoniou et al., 2021), we adopt five quantiles to represent different market conditions: extreme price drops (0.05 and 0.1), extreme price increases (0.9 and 0.95), and median (0.5). Consistently we use a 4-week forecast horizon. The total return connectedness among assets is 82% at the mean or median and about 94–95% under extreme conditions. This suggests that return connectedness is very strong and strengthens with shock size for both positive and negative shocks, indicating that return shocks spill over more intensely during extreme events, relative to normal periods. Moreover, their impact appears to be symmetric.

We again focus on three connectedness measures: total directional TO (Figure 13), FROM (Figure 14), and their difference, that is, NET (Figure 15). Figure 13 demonstrates that TotalEnergies, Eni, Shell, Aker, Equinor, BP, Repsol, Galp Energia SGPS, OMV, Subsea 7, and Tenaris send the largest amount of future uncertainty to others, both during extreme events and tranquil ("normal") periods. Notably, the spillover effect is significantly higher at the median than at extreme quantiles – see the black bars sticking out in these cases. These are strong and stable entities with diversified areas of activity. They are resistant to both internal and external shocks, thus guaranteeing the energy security of countries and entire regions. We observe the opposite results for stocks from emerging markets. In the case of these stocks, return shock spillovers to other markets increase significantly under extreme market conditions. The level of return spillover in extrema dominates the level in the median case and is more pronounced for negative information. Emerging market companies are more exposed to extreme events than international energy corporations from developed countries and become the source of uncertainty in the markets in the first place. When analyzing

Return connectedness

Figure 4: Net pairwise directional connectedness (NPDC) for oil, gas, and energy stocks during (a) 2018–2023, (b) 2018–2019, (c) 2020–2021, (d) 2022–2023.

Note: Blue (yellow) nodes imply net shock transmitters (receivers) and the size of the nodes relates to the absolute values of the net total directional connectedness. The direction of the arrows illustrates the direction of spillovers between two variables, and the thickness of the arrows implies the intensity of these spillovers.

spillovers FROM, presented in Figure 14, we notice that all assets, including oil and gas, experience approximately a similar level of shock transmission under extreme market conditions. Shock spillovers from others in the median differ more than those from extrema. Their highest values occur for the largest firms. Gas definitely stands out among all the assets and demonstrates disconnection from all others in terms of spillover in the median. Finally, the role of analyzed markets as net contributors/receivers is sensitive to the quantiles (Figure 15). More exactly, for most markets, the sign of the directional total net connectedness index does not change for different quantiles, but its value does. The highest net spillovers appear in the median and concern the largest firms – the main shock contributors to the system. All emerging markets are shock takers in almost all quantiles, overwhelmingly in the median.

Figure 5: Pairwise directional connectedness oil TO others.

Figure 6: Pairwise directional connectedness oil FROM others.

Finally, we examine the dynamic quantile connectedness among asset returns using the rolling QVAR(1) model with a fixed window size of 104. The rolling total connectedness index results for each quantile are presented in Figure 16. The horizontal axis of this chart represents the time component, while the vertical axis – the quantile. The color of the heat-map indicates the value of the TCI: when the TCI value is higher (lower), the color is warmer (cooler). Figure 16 confirms our main findings and displays the time-varying nature of the total connectedness index, which is higher during the economic slowdown caused by the COVID-19 pandemic than after the outbreak of the war

Figure 7: Pairwise directional connectedness gas TO others.

Figure 8: Pairwise directional connectedness gas FROM others.

in Ukraine, both at extreme quantiles and at the median. The Figure indicates the highest values of TCI both in lower and upper quantiles and the lowest values in the median. The latter decreases suddenly at the beginning of 2022, when the rolling window does no longer capture the beginning of the COVID-19 crash.

Figure 17 presents the rolling directional connectedness TO all others and Figure 18 rolling NET total directional connectedness for selected assets for each quantile. Colors in the heatmaps range from dark blue, presenting high-receiving, to dark red, meaning high-transmitting asset. The results are consistent with those obtained using the VAR

Figure 9: Dynamic total connectedness index (TCI) for oil, gas, and energy stocks.

Note: The black color indicates the connectedness measure for TVP-VAR. The red line represents window 104 (the green line – window 156) for LASSO-VAR.

system and confirm the impact of market capitalization and the sub-sector to which the company belongs, on its role as a net transmitter/receiver of shocks to/from the system. Eleven oil & gas companies from developed markets are the primary contributors to market shocks across most quantiles, especially between 0.2 and 0.8. For the sake of brevity, we only present plots for two representatives of this category i.e. TotalEnergies and Equinor (middle columns). The highest spillover to the system and equivalently the net spillover is found in the median area which weakens after the data behind the COVID-19 crash are considered. We obtain strikingly different results for the remaining firms. They absorb much more market shocks than they transmit, and the transmission only occurs in the extreme quantiles in specific periods (third column). Interestingly, Orlen (PKN.WA) joined the first group at the beginning of 2022, before it completed the acquisition of Grupa Lotos and PGNiG which was attributed to the Ukraine-Russia clash. The strengthening position of the company is reflected in the quantile plots. Since 2022 we can see the same transmission pattern as for the biggest firms i.e. increased transmission in the median. The spillovers from oil and gas exhibit highly dynamic features over time. The energy commodities generate spillover effects at high and low quantiles (slightly negative asymmetric) and much weaker in the median (first columns). Oil behaves as a net receiver during the COVID-19 pandemic and becomes a net transmitter in extrema in a later period. However, the gas changes its role in the system from a shock-absorbing asset to being disconnected. Net total directional connectedness plots for oil and gas look similarly to those for companies from beyond the oil & gas industry or emerging markets (e.g. IPEKE.IS). Thus, they do not play a significant role in the system.

Return connectedness

Figure 10: Dynamic directional connectedness TO all others for oil, gas, and energy stocks.

Note: The black color indicates the connectedness measure for TVP-VAR. The red line represents window 104 (the green line – window 156) for LASSO-VAR.

6. Discussion and conclusions

In the paper, we consider the Brent oil and natural gas markets and their connectedness with major European companies operating in the energy sector. The study covers the period from March 16, 2018, to December 29, 2023, and focuses on two periods exceptional for the energy sector, i.e. the COVID-19 pandemic and Russia's invasion of Ukraine. Since we study interrelation between 33 assets simultaneously, the Diebold and Yilmaz (2012) method is applied and its further extensions (TVP-VAR and QVAR).

We can summarize our findings as follows. First, in the whole analyzed period, oil and gas received more shocks from the energy companies than they transmitted to them. On one side, that can indicate the increased financialization of these markets, understood as the growth of the number of investors that speculate on the price of the commodities rather than possess them. On the other hand, the stocks included in our sample also represent the condition of companies that explore, produce, and refine oil and natural gas (e.g. Shell PLC, Equinor ASA, Eni SpA). Thus, their performance can affect oil and gas prices. Indeed, the companies-producers of oil and gas sent more shocks to other assets in the system than they received from others. The smallest companies (ranked by capitalization) and those beyond the oil & gas operations industry are net receivers of impulses from others.

Return connectedness

Figure 11: Dynamic directional connectedness FROM all others for oil, gas, and energy stocks.

Note: The black color indicates the connectedness measure for TVP-VAR. The red line represents window 104 (the green line – window 156) for LASSO-VAR.

We also note that the role of oil and gas in the system differs substantially. Natural gas sends significantly fewer impulses to the stocks than oil. Generally, the gas market behaves similarly to the stocks of emerging markets or smaller developed markets regarding shock transmission. That places natural gas and smaller companies as market shock recipients whose prices have only a local scope.

It is also crucial that oil and gas markets send impulses to other assets in the system when their prices experience extreme movements (high increases or decreases), and their reaction to impulses from other assets is reflected in the extreme movements of their prices, too. That is not the case for the large companies that affect other assets through moderate movements of their prices.

When analyzing connectedness in sub-periods, we note the increase in connectedness during turbulence periods – during COVID-19 and the moment of the outbreak of the Russo-Ukrainian war. Referring to the contagion definition of Forbes and Rigobon (2002), who distinguish between the contagion and interdependence relationships by studying the increase in linkages between assets, we can see clear evidence of contagion during the COVID-19 pandemic phase. We note that the increase in connectedness during COVID-19 was much higher than at the beginning of the war. That result confirms the findings of Gong and Xu (2022), who document that geopolitical act risk (related to broadly understood uncertainty) drives connectedness changes more than geopolitical threats (related directly to wars).

Return connectedness

Figure 12: Dynamic directional net connectedness for oil, gas, and energy stocks.

Note: The black color indicates the connectedness measure for TVP-VAR. The red line represents window 104 (the green line – window 156) for LASSO-VAR.

Eventually, the transmission of impulses in different quantiles (extreme increases and decreases) also evolved over time. First of all, total asset connectedness is higher during the economic slowdown caused by the COVID-19 pandemic than after the outbreak of the war in Ukraine, both at extreme quantiles and at the median. There is a clear difference between the large and small companies, though. The smallest companies absorb more market shocks than they transmit. Furthermore, they react mostly to extreme changes in the prices of large companies' stocks, and they respond to them also by extreme changes in their returns. On the contrary, the biggest companies affect the system through moderate price changes. The role of oil changed from net receiver during the pandemic to a net transmitter in extrema, while gas switched from shock absorber to being disconnected.

6.1. Policy implications

Transmission of shocks between assets or markets may significantly affect the key macroeconomic indicators, including inflation, unemployment, or production. Thus, the results of our study should be of interest not only to investors but also to policymakers. Our findings suggest that they should closely monitor the condition of the largest oil-producing companies to anticipate further changes in energy markets. It is crucial that these companies affect the markets usually through moderate changes in their prices. It is also worth noting that both oil/gas and the companies react strongly to widely understood geopolitical uncertainty and that such uncertainty affects the market for longer

Figure 13: Directional connectedness for oil, gas, and energy stocks: directional connectedness TO all others – quantile approach.

Figure 14: Directional connectedness for oil, gas, and energy stocks: directional connectedness FROM all others – quantile approach.

periods. On the contrary, war-related events impose a short-term reaction on the market (see also (Fiszeder and Malecka, 2022; Gong and Xu, 2022)).

The investors who earn on speculation in the energy-related market should bear in mind that the small companies react hectically to the extreme changes in prices not only of oil but also of other small companies. The reaction to moderate changes in the prices of major companies is reflected in the moderate changes in the prices of small

Figure 15: Directional connectedness for oil, gas, and energy stocks: directional NET total connectedness – quantile approach.

companies. Gas, as being almost disconnected from the movement in the companies’ prices, could potentially serve as a proper hedge or even safe haven in such a portfolio.

6.2. Limitations of the study

The study has some limitations. First, we analyze specific benchmarks of oil (Brent) and gas (TTF Netherlands). Change of the benchmarks to different frequencies of prices could alter the results. Besides, we concentrate on return connectedness, neglecting connectedness in volatility, where the relationships could be stronger.

7. Acknowledgements

The research was supported by the National Science Center in Poland through the project 2022/47/B/HS4/01194 "The impact of the Russo-Ukrainian conflict on prices and volatility of energy and crop commodities, and risk perception of European Union economies".

A. Appendix

In Table 2 we present descriptive statistics for asset returns.

A. Online Appendix

Tables A1 to A4 show the return connectedness for the entire period and three sub-periods.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Małgorzata Just: Conceptualization of this study, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Formal Analysis, Writing-Original draft preparation. **Agata Kliber:** Visualisation, Writing- original draft preparation, Funding acquisition. **Krzysztof Echaust:** Data curation, Investigation, Writing - Original draft preparation.

Return connectedness

Figure 16: Dynamic total connectedness index (TCI) for oil, gas, and stocks – quantile connectedness from 13.03.2020 to the end of 2023 (TCI QVAR, window of 104 observations).

Figure 17: Dynamic directional connectedness TO all others for oil, gas prices, and stocks – quantile connectedness from 13.03.2020 to the end of 2023 (window of 104 observations).

Return connectedness

Figure 18: Dynamic NET total directional connectedness for oil, gas prices, and stocks – quantile connectedness from 13.03.2020 to the end of 2023 (window of 104 observations).

Table 2
Descriptive statistics of asset returns.

	Min	Mean	Max	St. Dev.	Cor with LCOc1	Cor with TRNLTTFFVYc1
LCOc1	-29.071	0.050	31.352	6.014	1.000***	0.197***
TRNLTTFFVYc1	-56.036	0.188	31.319	8.393	0.197***	1.000***
SHEL.L	-40.767	0.020	25.636	4.952	0.513***	0.157***
BP.L	-41.882	-0.035	26.137	5.229	0.525***	0.142**
HBR.L	-140.900	-0.519	42.560	12.434	0.525***	0.134**
ENOG.L	-57.313	0.258	58.101	8.015	0.371***	0.111
TTEF.PA	-37.199	0.049	29.549	4.698	0.480***	0.132**
GTT.PA	-26.614	0.239	18.556	4.841	0.339***	0.163***
ENI.MI	-40.869	-0.007	17.384	4.631	0.555***	0.126**
SRG.MI	-26.680	0.039	9.165	3.296	0.190***	0.055
TENR.MI	-44.102	-0.008	23.121	5.871	0.509***	0.107
EQNR.OL	-36.291	0.105	15.604	5.116	0.631***	0.339***
AKRBP.OL	-71.184	0.032	28.149	7.607	0.658***	0.219***
SUBC.OL	-44.551	0.002	28.125	6.884	0.640***	0.172***
NEL.OL	-35.018	0.168	28.688	8.595	0.188***	0.076
VWS.CO	-28.097	0.267	20.804	5.870	0.171***	0.079
REP.MC	-25.736	-0.001	22.626	5.067	0.565***	0.162***
ENAG.MC	-26.340	-0.146	10.421	3.458	0.234***	0.075
NESTE.HE	-23.930	0.137	26.872	5.370	0.276***	0.129**
GALP.LS	-30.843	-0.085	20.802	4.919	0.556***	0.148**
OMVV.VI	-44.146	-0.095	22.300	5.507	0.451***	0.009
PKN.WA	-21.603	-0.144	14.955	5.378	0.359***	0.068
JSW.WA	-36.001	-0.311	45.361	8.745	0.292***	0.104
LWBP.WA	-26.001	-0.195	54.264	7.237	0.271***	0.149***
KCHOL.IS	-29.552	0.072	30.447	6.930	0.139**	0.069
TUPRS.IS	-24.640	0.164	24.461	6.795	0.264***	0.087
IPEKE.IS	-33.176	-0.070	27.669	8.305	0.141**	0.047
MOLB.BU	-23.024	-0.126	14.067	4.306	0.239***	0.002
ROSNP.BX	-26.068	0.204	10.979	4.128	0.309***	0.078
SNG.BX	-20.405	0.068	13.131	3.760	0.281***	0.079
TGN.BX	-24.249	-0.165	15.855	3.767	0.126**	-0.044
MORr.AT	-21.082	0.023	22.610	5.041	0.312***	0.052
HEPr.AT	-20.574	-0.067	14.629	4.276	0.307***	0.083

Note: Cor means Pearson correlation between assets and oil (gas); *** and ** indicate the significance at the 1% level and the 5% level, respectively. The horizontal line separates developed and emerging markets.

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